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A&E dept

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**REPORT OF QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT ON PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE ON HAND
HYGIENE AND PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT AT A&E DEPARTMENT.**

Background: Infection prevention and control is the challenge encountered in emergency departments as it is primary point of access to timely and life-saving medical care for acutely ill or injured patients(Liang, Riethman, and Fox 2018). These patients not only have the potential to spread communicable infectious diseases to healthcare personnel and other patients, but are vulnerable to acquiring new infections associated with the care they receive(Liang et al. 2014). Furthermore, in periods of outbreak, these transmissions can be devastating for health professionals if infection prevention and control compliance is not robust(Green 2014). Nosocomial infections are favored by, mostly, healthcare workers who has adequate knowledge and who display a positive attitude, but practices toward infection control are not sufficient(Alshathri 2021)(Chisanga 2017). Behind this, gaps have been identified in knowledge and practice of infection control among doctors and nurses(Iliyasu et al. 2016). Low compliance towards infection prevention and control guidelines is a possible cause of hospital acquired infections in health care providers and patients(Bahegwa et al. 2022). At King Faisal Hospital(KFH), it has been reported that large proportion of nursing team have negative attitudes and poor infection prevention and control practices fault to gaps of knowledge in infection prevention and control(Nepomuscene 2021). These gaps and practices would not still reign at emergency department and this QIP was designed to evaluate practical knowledge of IPC at Emergency Department so that any gap in knowledge could be corrected.

The aim of this project is to protect patients, visitors and staff at Accident and Emergency Department at KFH, from acquiring an infection and to control infection transmission.

Method: This study was an observational survey evaluation of practical knowledge of infection prevention and control for health care providers at Accident and Emergency Department at KING FAISAL HOSPITAL. The study was completed in one week and data collected on 7th, 8th, 10th and 11th of November 2022 by distributing questionnaires to health care providers (doctors, nurses, and hygiene and sanitation officers) after morning reports and filled immediately. Questions covered practical knowledge of personal protective equipment & donning, hand hygiene practices by hand washing with soap and water, and use of alcohol-based hand sanitizer. Every health care provider who came in morning reports on above mentioned date was candidate to the survey. Exclusion criteria were unwillingness to

participate to the survey. Responses were collected and analyzed in excel format. For questions with multiple correct responses, if all correct responses less than 50%, this is considered as failed question when aggregates are being collected. Questionnaires will be attached to this report.

Results A total of 23 questionnaires were distributed and all returned to investigator. No one was excluded from the survey. All questions were being counted on 37points. The lowest note was 5 and highest 29. Median note is 22, Mode 26, average 21.91. Aggregates were collected in three groups of questions; use of personal protective equipments (PPE) and donning questions, hand hygiene with soap and water, and alcohol based hand sanitizers. Average of respondents who gave correct answers for PPE and donning is 56%. For Hand hygiene practical knowledge, the respondents with correct answers was 59%. Lastly, for questions on practical knowledge on Alcohol based hand sanitizer, average of respondents with right answers was 51.5%. For all three groups, average of giving correct answers is 55.5%.

Conclusion: Based on the above survey results, there is a big gap of practical knowledge of infection prevention and control. There is an urgent need to close the gap by training of health care providers of Accident and Emergency as below:

Training can be classified under five main headings:

1. Basic training, as part of medical, nursing or other vocational curricula;
2. Induction courses for new entrants into hospital staff;
3. Refresher courses for doctors, nurses and others, at intervals of several years, to refresh their knowledge and bring it up to date;
4. Special courses for Infection Control Nurses and others specializing in hospital infection;
5. Meetings, courses or symposia on particular procedures or aspects of hospital infection and its control. (Suparyanto dan Rosad (2015 2020).

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